

A Bibliometric Analysis of Systemic Immune Inflammatory Indices in Emergency Medicine:
Global Research Trends From 2020 to 2025

Original Article

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ABSTRACT

Background: Systemic immune inflammatory indices derived from complete blood count parameters have gained increasing attention in emergency medicine as rapid, accessible biomarkers for risk stratification and prognostic assessment. Although their clinical utility has been widely investigated, the global research landscape, thematic evolution and structural characteristics of this literature have not yet been comprehensively evaluated.

Methods: A bibliometric analysis was conducted using data retrieved from the Web of Science Core Collection. Original research articles published in English between 2020 and 2025 that investigated systemic immune inflammatory indices in emergency department settings were included. Performance analysis was performed to assess publication trends, citation patterns, and the productivity of countries, institutions and journals. Science mapping techniques, including keyword co occurrence and collaboration network analyses, were applied to explore thematic structures and research hotspots.

Results: A total of 359 original articles were included. Annual publication output increased markedly between 2020 and 2022, followed by a sustained volume of publications through 2025. The mean number of citations per article was 7.35 (median 3; IQR 9), and the mean citation density was 1.88 (median 1.00; IQR 2.25). Türkiye was the leading contributing country with 154 publications (42.9%), followed by China (41; 11.4%) and the United States (28; 7.8%). The American Journal of Emergency Medicine demonstrated the highest overall citation impact, while multidisciplinary journals showed higher mean citation rates. Keyword analyses identified emergency department, mortality, COVID-19 and prognosis as central themes, with a temporal shift toward outcome focused and decision support oriented research.

Conclusion: Research on systemic immune inflammatory indices in emergency medicine has expanded rapidly in recent years and evolved toward clinically relevant outcomes and prognostic applications.

Keywords: Systemic immune inflammatory indices, Complete blood count, Emergency department, Bibliometric analysis

Introduction

In a substantial proportion of patients presenting to the emergency department (ED), the underlying pathophysiological

processes are centered on the immune response. A wide spectrum of clinical conditions, including infectious diseases, sepsis, acute respiratory failure, cardiovascular emergencies, and acute

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surgical pathologies, are directly associated with the magnitude and regulation of inflammation and immune activation [1]. Given the overcrowded nature of emergency departments, the high volume of patient admissions, the limited time available for clinical decision-making, and the critical importance of early intervention, there is a growing need for rapid, reproducible, and readily accessible biomarkers to estimate prognosis in these complex clinical scenarios [2, 3]. In this context, objective biomarkers that can be used for early risk stratification and prediction of clinical course have gained increasing importance in emergency medicine practice [4].

Complete blood count (CBC) is one of the most frequently requested and rapidly available laboratory tests in the emergency department and provides direct information on the core cellular components of inflammation and immune response [5]. Neutrophil, lymphocyte, monocyte, and platelet counts reflect distinct aspects of immune activation and offer valuable insights into disease severity in acute conditions. Beyond the isolated use of these individual parameters, systemic immune inflammatory indices derived from the ratios or combinations of cellular components aim to more accurately capture the dynamic interplay between inflammation and immune balance [6, 7]. This approach offers a substantial advantage in the emergency setting, as it is simple, reproducible and easily integrable into routine clinical practice.

In recent years, CBC based systemic immune inflammatory indices have expanded considerably beyond earlier markers such as the neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio (NLR) and platelet to lymphocyte ratio (PLR), with the development of more complex, multicomponent indices. Measures such as the systemic immune inflammation index

(SII), systemic inflammatory response index (SIRI), and aggregate inflammation index (AISI) provide more comprehensive frameworks designed to simultaneously reflect inflammatory activity, immune suppression, and platelet response [8, 9]. These indices have been extensively investigated in high risk clinical conditions commonly encountered in the emergency department, including COVID-19, sepsis, acute respiratory failure, cardiovascular emergencies, trauma, and acute surgical pathologies [8, 10-14].

Nevertheless, heterogeneity in patient populations, variability in outcome definitions, and the lack of standardized cutoff values for these biomarkers have led to considerable methodological diversity across studies and substantial differences in the comparability of results [15]. Conflicting findings have been reported regarding the prognostic performance of the same index across different clinical scenarios, and there is currently no clear consensus on which indices provide superior prognostic value in specific clinical contexts. Although the number of studies examining the use of systemic immune inflammatory indices in emergency department related conditions has increased steadily, a comprehensive evaluation of the global distribution, structural characteristics, and temporal evolution of this scientific output is still lacking. According to our Web of Science (WoS) search, between 2000 and 2025, a total of 717 original articles have been published, 532 of which appeared within the last five years.

The present study provides the first bibliometric analysis of research focusing on the use of systemic immune inflammatory indices in the emergency department. By examining articles published between 2020 and 2025, we aim to map global research output, identify publication and citation trends, highlight

leading countries, institutions, and journals, explore author collaboration networks, and delineate thematic research clusters, thereby summarizing the developmental trajectory of this emerging field. Through this systematic overview, we seek to present a structured synthesis of the existing literature and to offer a guiding reference for future clinical and methodological research.

Materials and Methods

Data Source

This study presents a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of the scientific literature related to systemic immune-inflammatory indices in emergency medicine, focusing on original research articles published between 2020 and 2025. All bibliographic data were retrieved from the Web of Science Core Collection (WoSCC), which was selected as the sole data source because of its standardized indexing system and its widespread acceptance in bibliometric research. WoSCC provides detailed and consistent bibliographic information, including article titles, abstracts, author keywords, author and institutional identifiers, country affiliations, journal sources, citation counts, and reference lists, thereby enabling robust performance analysis and science-mapping procedures.

All records identified through the search were exported in the “Full Record and Cited References” format. Following data export, preprocessing steps (including data cleaning, duplicate removal, and variable harmonization) were applied to construct the final analytical dataset used for bibliometric evaluation.

Search strategy

The literature search was conducted in the WoSCC on December 20, 2025, to identify publications addressing systemic immune-

inflammatory indices within the context of emergency medicine. The search strategy was designed to capture both the full terminology and commonly used abbreviations of complete blood count-derived inflammatory indices, as well as to ensure relevance to the emergency department setting.

A Topic Search (TS), which queries article titles, abstracts, and author keywords, was performed using the following search expression: TS =("Neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio" OR NLR OR "Systemic immune inflammation index" OR SII OR "Aggregate index of systemic inflammation" OR AISI OR "Platelet to lymphocyte ratio" OR PLR OR "Monocyte to lymphocyte ratio" OR MLR OR "Systemic inflammation response index" OR SIRI) AND ("Emergency Department" OR "Emergency Room" OR "Emergency Medicine" OR "ED").

To evaluate contemporary research trends, the search was restricted to English-language original research articles published between January 1, 2020, and December 20, 2025. Only records indexed in the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-Expanded) and the Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI) were considered eligible. All retrieved records were exported in the “Full Record and Cited References” format for subsequent screening and analysis.

Eligibility criteria

Only original research articles were eligible for inclusion in the bibliometric analysis. Studies were included if they met all of the following criteria:

- (1) investigated at least one systemic immune-inflammatory index derived from complete blood count parameters (e.g., NLR, PLR, SII, SIRI, or AISI);
- (2) were conducted in an emergency department or acute care context;

(3) were published in English; and
(4) contained complete and consistent bibliographic information required for bibliometric evaluation.

Review articles, meta-analyses, editorials, letters, conference abstracts, case reports, and studies not directly related to emergency medicine or systemic immune-inflammatory indices were excluded. Records with incomplete, duplicated, or inconsistent bibliographic data were also excluded from the final dataset.

Study selection process

The initial search results were first screened according to document type and language restrictions. Non-article publications were excluded. The remaining records were then limited to the predefined publication period (January 1, 2020–December 20, 2025).

Subsequently, titles, abstracts, and author keywords were independently screened to assess relevance to systemic immune-inflammatory indices in emergency medicine. Publications that did not primarily focus on these indices or were not related to the emergency department setting were excluded. Following this multistep screening process, a total of 359 original research articles were included in the final bibliometric analysis. The study selection process was conducted in accordance with the principles of the PRISMA 2020 flow framework, and the selection steps are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for study selection.

Data Extraction and Preprocessing

For each included publication, the following bibliographic fields were extracted: article title, abstract, author keywords, author names, number of authors, institutional affiliations, country information, source journal, publication year, citation counts, Web of Science subject categories, and WoS accession numbers. To reduce inconsistencies, name harmonization procedures were applied to author, institution, and country fields. Variations in spelling and naming conventions were standardized using unified formats. Institutional and country information was derived from both corresponding-author affiliations and the full list of contributing affiliations.

Journal impact metrics, including five-year Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and quartile classifications, were assigned by matching WoS records with the corresponding Journal Citation Reports (JCR) data. For articles published in 2025, the most recent available quartile information from the 2024 JCR release was used. Within the keyword dataset, synonymous terms and spelling variants were merged, and

redundant or semantically overlapping keywords were unified to ensure consistency in keyword-based analyses.

Bibliometric Analysis

Performance Analysis

Performance analysis was conducted to evaluate annual publication trends, citation patterns, authorship characteristics, and the productivity of countries, institutions, and journals. Citation indicators included total citation counts and the mean number of citations per article. To account for differences in publication time, citation density was calculated by dividing the total number of citations by the number of years elapsed since publication. This time-adjusted metric enabled more accurate comparisons of citation impact across publications from different years.

Science Mapping

Science-mapping analyses were performed to identify the conceptual structure and temporal evolution of the literature. Keyword co-occurrence analysis based on author keywords was used to visualize thematic clusters and research hotspots. Overlay visualization techniques were applied to illustrate temporal trends and citation impact across keywords. In addition, country-level collaboration networks were constructed to depict geographic contributions and international research partnerships within the field of emergency department-focused immune-inflammatory indices.

Software and Tools

All bibliometric analyses were conducted using the R software environment (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria). The bibliometrix package and its web-based interface, Biblioshiny, were used for performance analysis and

keyword-based evaluations. VOSviewer software was employed to generate country-level collaboration maps and keyword co-occurrence networks. Microsoft Excel was used for data organization, descriptive statistics, and the preparation of summary tables and figures.

Results

A total of 359 original research articles published between 2020 and 2025 were included in the final bibliometric analysis. The annual distribution of publications showed a progressive increase over time, with 30 articles in 2020, 60 in 2021, and a peak of 81 articles in 2022, followed by 63 publications in 2023, 59 in 2024, and 65 articles in 2025. Across the entire dataset, the mean number of citations per article was 7.35, with a median of 3 citations (IQR: 9). When adjusted for publication time, the mean citation density was 1.88, while the median citation density was 1.00 (IQR: 2.25). Analysis of authorship patterns revealed a mean of 6.20 authors per article, with a median of 6 authors (IQR: 4).

Annual Publication Trend

The annual publication trend is illustrated in Figure 2. Research output increased markedly from 30 articles in 2020 to 60 in 2021, reaching a peak of 81 publications in 2022. This was followed by a relative decline in 2023 ($n = 63$) and 2024 ($n = 59$), with a subsequent rise in 2025 ($n = 66$).

Figure 2 Annual Publication Trend

Purple bars represent the annual number of publications, while the yellow line connects yearly publication counts to illustrate temporal changes. The red marker highlights the year with the highest publication output.

Most Cited Articles

The ten most cited articles included in the analysis accumulated citation counts ranging from 40 to 146. The most highly cited study was published in 2021 by Seyit et al., reporting 146 citations with a citation density of 29.2. Overall, the majority of the top-cited publications originated from Türkiye, followed by contributions from Italy, Spain, Canada, Germany, and China. Publication years of the most influential articles were predominantly clustered between 2020 and 2022, and citation density values ranged from 10.0 to 37.3, indicating substantial variability in citation impact over time. Review of the ten most cited articles showed that these studies predominantly investigated prognostic inflammatory indices in COVID-19, general emergency department populations, acute pancreatitis, neurological conditions, trauma-related acute care settings, and pediatric cohorts (Table 1).

Distribution by Countries and Institutions

The geographic distribution of publications based on corresponding author affiliations is summarized in Table 2. Türkiye emerged as the leading contributor to the literature, followed by the People's Republic of China and the United States, with notable variation in publication output and citation impact across countries. Institution-level analysis based on first-author affiliations identified the University of Health Sciences Turkey as the most productive center, followed by several high-output academic

and training hospitals. Consistent with these findings, the country-level density visualization in Figure 3 illustrates the geographic concentration and intensity of research activity within the emergency department-focused inflammatory index literature.

Figure 3: Country-level publication density map

The density visualization illustrates the global distribution of publications based on country-level co-authorship, with color intensity reflecting the relative volume of scientific output.

Journal and Quartile Distribution

The distribution of publications across journals is summarized in Table 3. The included studies were disseminated across a broad range of journals, with the highest publication volumes observed in *Annals of Clinical and Analytical Medicine*, *American Journal of Emergency Medicine*, and *Journal of Clinical Medicine*. Journals with higher impact metrics, including *Scientific Reports* and *Frontiers in Medicine*, demonstrated greater average citation counts, whereas several specialty and regional journals contributed substantially to publication volume. Overall, a considerable proportion of the most productive journals were classified within Q1 and Q2 quartiles.

WoS Subject Category Analysis

The classification of the included studies across Web of Science subject categories is

presented in Figure 4. The majority of publications were indexed under Medicine, General & Internal (26.4%) and Emergency Medicine (15.3%), together accounting for more than two-fifths of the dataset. Additional contributions were observed in Pediatrics (4.5%), Medicine, Research & Experimental (4.1%), and Surgery (4.1%), while smaller proportions were distributed across Multidisciplinary Sciences (3.2%), Critical Care Medicine (2.9%), and neurologically oriented categories, including Clinical Neurology (2.7%) and Neurosciences (2.7%). A limited number of publications were further classified under Immunology (2.3%) and other less frequent subject categories.

Figure 4. Distribution of Publications Across Web of Science Categories

Keyword Co-Occurrence and Temporal Distribution

The overlay visualization of keyword co-occurrence is presented in Figure 5. Frequently occurring keywords were centered around emergency department, mortality, COVID-19, and prognosis, reflecting the core focus of the literature. Keywords associated with higher citation impact, indicated by warmer colors, were primarily related to COVID-19, pneumonia, sepsis, and acute ischemic stroke, whereas lower-cited terms were more commonly linked to general inflammatory markers and hematological parameters.

Figure 5. Overlay visualization of keyword co-occurrence analysis based on author keywords.

Node size represents the frequency of keyword occurrence, while link thickness indicates the strength of co-occurrence between keywords. Colors reflect the average citation impact of publications associated with each keyword, ranging from lower (blue) to higher citation density (yellow-red).

Discussions

This study represents the first comprehensive bibliometric analysis providing a panoramic overview of scientific production over the past five years regarding the use of systemic inflammatory markers, including SII, SIRI, AISI, NLR, and PLR, in emergency medicine practice. In the present analysis, 359 original articles published between 2020 and 2025 were examined and publication trends, citation dynamics, country and institutional productivity, journal profiles, and keyword clustering patterns were evaluated in an integrated manner.

Analysis of annual publication trends revealed a sharp increase during the 2020 to 2022 period, which appears to be largely associated with the heightened demand for inflammatory biomarkers during the COVID-19 pandemic [10, 16-18]. Clinically, this pattern may be interpreted as a reflection of the increased need for rapid risk stratification in emergency departments

during the pandemic period. Complete blood count based, low cost and rapidly available indices such as NLR, PLR and SII were extensively tested not only in COVID-19 but also in other acute emergency conditions including sepsis, pneumonia and acute respiratory failure. Notably, publication volumes did not decline below a certain threshold even in the post pandemic period and demonstrated a renewed upward trend in 2025. This finding suggests that systemic immune inflammatory indices are not merely a transient research interest limited to the pandemic context but rather constitute a sustained research domain across a broad clinical spectrum, including sepsis, acute respiratory failure, cardiovascular emergencies and neurological emergencies. Indeed, recent studies have reported the prognostic value of these indices in non COVID emergency conditions such as acute ischemic stroke, traumatic brain injury and acute heart failure [19-23].

When the overall citation burden was evaluated, the mean number of citations per article was 7.35 (median 3; IQR 9), and the mean citation density was 1.88 (median 1.00; IQR 2.25). Although publications from the 2020 to 2022 period exhibited higher cumulative citation counts, interpretation of the lower citation numbers observed for articles published in 2025 should account for the time dependent nature of citation accrual. For this reason, time sensitive metrics such as citation density were incorporated into the analysis. The ten most cited articles received between 40 and 146 citations, with the highest cited study published in 2021 [24]. Furthermore, the clustering of highly cited studies within the 2020 to 2022 period likely reflects both the heightened visibility associated with the pandemic and the longer citation window available to studies published during the early phase of this research surge.

The most striking finding regarding country level contribution was Türkiye's clear leadership based on first author affiliation, with 154 publications (42.9%), followed by China (41; 11.4%) and the United States (28; 7.8%). This distribution is consistent with increased interest in rapid decision support biomarkers in countries with high emergency department patient volumes. In Türkiye, the high burden of emergency department visits, the need for rapid clinical decision making and the widespread availability of complete blood count testing may have enhanced the research attractiveness of these indices [1, 25]. Conversely, some countries demonstrated higher mean citation values, such as China with 9.46, Taiwan with 9.60 and Greece with 11.40, suggesting the production of fewer but more highly visible or impactful studies. These differences may be related to factors such as journal selection, the proportion of publications in Q1 or Q2 journals, study design characteristics including prospective or multicenter approaches, the breadth of the target population and whether the study proposed broadly applicable indices. At the institutional level, productivity was concentrated in large teaching and research hospitals and centers with high patient volumes, a pattern commonly reported in the literature and consistent with expectations for emergency department based research.

Regarding journal distribution, *Annals of Clinical and Analytical Medicine*, *American Journal of Emergency Medicine* and *Journal of Clinical Medicine* were among the most prolific sources. However, when impact was considered, the *American Journal of Emergency Medicine* demonstrated strong performance in terms of both total citations and mean citations per article, while *Scientific Reports* achieved a high average citation rate despite a lower number of publications. This observation suggests that when systemic immune inflammatory

indices are framed within the context of clinical decision support in emergency care, they may resonate more strongly in multidisciplinary journals with broader readership.

Web of Science category analysis indicated that the majority of publications were classified under Medicine, General & Internal and Emergency Medicine, with smaller but meaningful contributions from pediatrics, surgery and critical care. This distribution suggests that the application of these indices extends beyond a narrow emergency medicine focus and encompasses interdisciplinary domains including internal medicine, intensive care, infectious diseases and surgical emergencies. Consistently, the thematic focus of the most highly cited studies included COVID-19, general emergency department populations, acute pancreatitis, neurological conditions, trauma and pediatric cohorts, supporting the expanding clinical scope of this research area [11, 26-30].

Keyword co occurrence and overlay analyses clearly delineated the thematic core of the literature. Emergency department, mortality, COVID-19 and prognosis were central nodes within the network, while higher citation density was concentrated around clinically severe and high mortality conditions such as COVID-19, sepsis, pneumonia and acute ischemic stroke. Early studies predominantly emphasized general hematological parameters, whereas later publications increasingly focused on clinical outcomes, suggesting an evolution of the field from a descriptive phase toward a clinical decision support oriented phase [21, 31, 32]. Word cloud visualization further supported this transition, demonstrating that the most frequently recurring concepts in the literature are directly related to emergency department practice.

From a pathophysiological perspective, systemic immune inflammatory indices are thought to reflect the integrated response of innate immunity, adaptive immune suppression, and platelet mediated inflammatory amplification during acute stress states. In acute ischemic stroke, elevated indices such as NLR, SII, and SIRI have been associated with infarct volume, blood brain barrier disruption, secondary immune suppression and unfavorable neurological outcomes, supporting the concept that these markers capture both acute inflammatory activation and post ischemic immune dysregulation [33-35]. Similarly, in acute coronary syndromes, higher values of CBC derived indices have been linked to plaque instability, endothelial dysfunction, thrombotic burden and short term mortality, suggesting a close relationship between systemic inflammation, platelet activation and adverse cardiovascular prognosis [36-39]. In trauma and acute surgical emergencies, these indices have been shown to correlate with injury severity, systemic inflammatory response, coagulopathy and multiorgan dysfunction, reinforcing their role as surrogate markers of global physiological stress rather than disease specific biomarkers [14, 29, 40]. Collectively, the existing literature supports the prognostic relevance of systemic immune inflammatory indices in acute, high risk emergency conditions by framing them as reflections of the host response to ischemia, tissue injury and systemic inflammation.

Despite this growing body of evidence in classical acute emergencies, an important gap in the literature concerns the application of systemic immune inflammatory indices in the context of chronic diseases presenting with acute exacerbations. While chronic inflammatory and autoinflammatory disorders such as familial Mediterranean fever, inflammatory bowel disease, and systemic autoimmune conditions are characterized by well described baseline

inflammatory profiles, studies specifically evaluating these indices during acute emergency department presentations remain limited [41-44]. Moreover, most emergency medicine studies rely on a single blood sample obtained at admission, with very few investigations assessing serial measurements or short term temporal changes in inflammatory indices during emergency department observation or early inpatient follow up. This represents a critical limitation, as the dynamic evolution of the immune inflammatory response may provide additional prognostic and monitoring value beyond single time point assessment. Expanding the use of these indices from one time diagnostic tools toward longitudinal markers of clinical trajectory could enhance their utility in patient follow up, treatment response assessment and risk stratification across a broader spectrum of emergency presentations. Addressing these underexplored areas may therefore represent an important opportunity for future research and further integration of systemic immune inflammatory indices into emergency medicine practice.

Taken together, these findings indicate that systemic immune inflammatory indices have established a strong presence in emergency medicine research. Nevertheless, the lack of standardized cutoff values, heterogeneity of patient populations and variability in outcome definitions remain key limitations to clinical applicability. Future research should prioritize multivariable models that integrate these indices with clinical scores, vital signs and other biomarkers rather than evaluating them in isolation, thereby facilitating translation into clinical practice. In addition, prospective and multicenter study designs will be essential to improve the generalizability of findings.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. The analysis was restricted to the Web of Science Core Collection database and studies indexed in other databases may have been excluded. Bibliometric indicators are inherently time sensitive and citation counts for recently published articles may therefore appear artificially low. Moreover, bibliometric analyses do not provide a direct assessment of the methodological quality of individual studies.

Conclusion

In summary, the present bibliometric analysis demonstrates that research on systemic immune inflammatory indices in emergency medicine has expanded rapidly over the past five years, evolving from exploratory descriptive studies toward clinically oriented prognostic and decision support applications. The literature increasingly frames these indices as integrative markers of the host response to acute ischemia, tissue injury and systemic inflammatory stress, with consistent associations reported across a wide range of high risk emergency conditions, including cerebrovascular, cardiovascular, infectious and traumatic presentations.

At the same time, important gaps remain. The lack of standardized cutoff values, reliance on single time point measurements and substantial heterogeneity in study populations and outcome definitions limit both comparability and clinical translation. Notably, the relative scarcity of studies addressing chronic inflammatory and autoinflammatory diseases presenting with acute exacerbations highlights an underexplored but clinically relevant research area within emergency medicine. Expanding future investigations to include serial measurements, acute on chronic inflammatory states and integrated multivariable models that combine immune inflammatory indices with clinical scores

and vital parameters may substantially enhance their utility for patient monitoring and risk stratification. Although systemic immune-inflammatory indices represent accessible and promising tools in emergency medicine, their transition into routine clinical practice necessitates validation through large-scale, prospective multicenter studies.

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